

SIMPLIFIED ROLLING CALCULATIONS: PART 4 AN EXAMPLE OF COUPLING 2 DEGREE OF FREEDOM (DOF) OR MORE

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ABSTRACT

This paper is the fourth installment in the series dealing with the rolling motion (and other motions). Here the emphasis is on the coupling between roll and heave and sometime with other motions. The focus on the physics of the movement as opposed to the establishment's "scientists" (the supper famous Dr. Yamaka (Borat), or equivalent Faltinsen, Fossen, the late Landweber and Stern, etc) ideas which violate the undergird of the basics of physics laws. It explicitly indicates that this work conflicts and contradicts with almost all the works in the area on this topic. As it can be observed, the establishment models/concepts contain the wrong pivot points, the usage of the erroneous added mass matrix, etc are still (heavily) used in the industry even though these concepts violate the basics laws of physics. There is no such thing like m_{14} or a_{14} such nonsense to couple between the DOF (degree of freedom) but simply physics based connections.

This paper is an extension or an example of the previous paper dealt in general with the coupling between the different DOFs. As stated before, this paper is more specific and deals with only limited cases and focuses on the governing equations. Additionally, as a by product, it seems that these equations and presentations provide explanation to the phenomenon known as parametric rolling and slamming. Now when the fallacies about the added mass matrix etc exposed which includes the right pivot points locations and the transfer properties acknowledged, the governing equations can be written for the specific case of roll and heave.

This paper intended to present the actual governing equations but not to solve them for any specific case. Even just writing the right equations is a massive progress because of the erroneous models have plagued this industry. Every DOF has its own dis-

tinctive requirements and quirks and hence it is not easy to write general instructions suitable for all cases. Hence, a presentation of the coupling case for the heave and the roll is exhibited. Seeing the fundamentals and fatal errors dominating the field for more 150 years, it is prayed that no new errors are replacing the old one and thus this work points to the weak points or not clear. Hence, there is a standing request, please challenge these ideas, this article is not just to point to the establishment's fallacies (obviously), but if there is an error in this work, the error should be squashed and leave only presentation of actual physics work.

NOMENCLATURE

Points of Interest

$\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{A}', \mathcal{A}''$ Pivot point at the liquid level

b Width of the body

\bar{b} The ratio of b_1/b_2

\mathcal{B} Buoyancy centroid

\mathcal{G} Mass centroid

\mathcal{K} Keel

\mathcal{M} Metacenter none existent and imaginary point

\emptyset Point on vertical after input angle

\mathcal{Z} A point on \mathcal{GM} perpendicular to \mathcal{B}

Λ A point on the liquid line crossing the counter left side

χ A point on the liquid line crossing the counter rightside

Variables

a trapezoid dimension Coefficient

b trapezoid dimension Coefficient

c trapezoid dimension Coefficient

D Total Ship (body) height

\mathcal{D} New distance $\mathcal{B}'\emptyset$

d Ship draught

- g Gravity constant
- I Moment of inertia either body or liquid
- \mathcal{L} Lagrangian
- L Angular momentum
- m Mass
- s Ship Length
- t Time
- \mathcal{T} Kinetic energy
- \mathcal{U} Potential energy
- w Ship weight
- \mathfrak{X} Horizontal distance to the original pivot point
- x Distance in straight (movement) direction
- y Distance perpendicular to x

Greek Letters

- α Absolute value of difference angle right to left
- β Triangle letter as α sometimes
- ω Angular velocity
- ϕ Angle based on pivot at G (commonly undefined)
- ρ Density
- θ Input Angle
- ξ The angle $\angle AJA'$

Subscripts

- 0 Old location
- add, a Added mass/force
- b Floating body (ship)
- l left
- r right
- xx Around the x coordinate

Key Words

Ship Coupling Rolling–Heaving, Degree of Freedom Coupling, Transfer Properties, Added Mass Matrix, Decoupling

1 Introduction

A review will be followed by the construction of the governing equations and later a comparison to the establishment’ “models” is discussed. There is no need to dwell on how backward was the marine industry before this series was published as these errors were discussed previously ([Bar-Meir 2023d](#); [Bar-Meir 2024a](#); [Bar-Meir 2023b](#); [Bar-Meir 2023f](#); [Bar-Meir 2023c](#); [Bar-Meir 2023b](#); [Bar-Meir 2023a](#); [Bar-Meir 2022a](#); [Bar-Meir and Altschul 2024](#)). Generally speaking before Landweber’s work (1963) which introduced the erroneous added mass matrix, the coupling, selection of DOF, and equations were based on specific author. The pivot point was assumed to be in different locations (sometime at the metacenter and sometimes at the mass centroid! Why no one asked any question for example, how possible these two conflicting points coexist in the same time?) while mostly the coupling was assumed to be non existed. After Landweber (1963) introduction of the infamous erroneous

theory of the added mass matrix (only for the linear velocities, the rotational part was introduced/promoted by Faltinsen and colleagues), the “real” coupling started. Since the introduction of these erroneous concepts, innumerable papers were written based on these faulty ideas. What a waste of resources! On the other hand, several numerical techniques and perturbation methods were developed and in this sense some contributions were made.

The first installment of this series ([Bar-Meir 2023g](#)) briefly discussed the history of what people assumed the pivot point locations are for the marine industry (these are most common options: metacenter, mass centroid, ether “æther”) and the violations of the second law by these choices with the exception of the æther (hard to analyze issues dealing with æther). In the second installment ([Bar-Meir 2024b](#)) the horizontal movement of the pivot point caused because unsymmetry body during the rolling period was mentioned and discussed. The paper introduces the rsymmetry concept. Perhaps the most important paper in this series and therefore the marine industry in the last 150 years is the paper ([Bar-Meir 2024c](#)). This paper discusses the coupling between the various DOFs. These installments exhibit the errors in the establishment’s theory/model/concept, first required a change from the belief in the GM to the actual element AG and second: the effects of the abrupt and continuous contours on period. Third, the removal of the added mass matrix idea and additionally the usage of the physics based concepts to describe the coupling which clear the way for physics based models. This instalment deals with a specific coupling or connection among the rolling to other “degree of freedoms” as heave. In this connection, the pivot point is moving vertically (up and down)¹. The fifth installment deals with the added parallel transfer theorem for the added moment of inertia is pushed to hiatus. The comprehensive study of the transfer properties hopefully will appear in a different series (a very large job for one individual) hopefully soon. All these works are considered as a rough draft to be summarized in the stability book ([Bar-Meir 2022b](#)).

While it is not pleasant to find out that your work is total trash but this topic is science and there are only two options either to accept the correct ideas or reject them. Clearly no one is willing to defend the establishment ideas as the call for for disputation never has been answered. Only several empty promises of providing explanation(s) for establishment’s ideas and several demands from “scientists” not discuss their errors (for example, Metin Taylan from Istanbul). No one has been willing to answer/defend but some still publish their pa-

pers full errors but now many are making the papers inaccessible. While in a short term this procedure looks like a solution for the researcher, consider how it looks in the long term.

Observing the fatal errors produced in this field which derailed the research for hundreds of years suggests that one has to be humble. Thus, even with the excitement and pride of all these discoveries which change almost whole undersigning of marine engineering, and solid–fluid interaction, etc is hoped that no new major errors will be introduced to replace the old ones. This author see himself as someone who is cable of making mistakes. If one find a mistake or more, please challenge or inform any work/error in this series or any other work by this author.

2 History of the Rolling Coupling

There two sources/causes for the rolling: one) application of a torque on the ship (in the right direction) two) instability in other degree of freedom (DOF) (normally heave) which leads to instability causing rolling (Bar-Meir 2022b). The first source can be a wave or a series of waves, wind (periodic), and mechanical change in the ship (abrupt or variable with time). In 18xx the approach was to look at the movements as independent. For example, (Scribanti 1903; Scribanti 1904) assumed the coupling is due to the connection of the righting arm only. It can be observed that Scribanti had probably the best instinct for his time on the physics.

The added mass (the matrix) was assumed as the core (if not sole) cause of the coupling of the different degrees. Hence a discussion on the added mass is a must. While the added mass started to be used in the late in 192x no one beside von Karman (1929) realized the added mass effect on floating bodies. Yet, no one has checked the stability of the heave motion. As a side note, Fitzgerald (1909) work dealt with the flying insects and thus it can be said that it is not exactly and directly related to floating bodies these advances were rejected (why?). Sezawa et al (1938) observed that the roll coupled with the ship speed increase the frequency. Notice that this coupling is about the actual velocity value and not surge (surge is deviation from the average velocity). This claim is the first to relate DOF with the transfer property of the ship (transfer property related to the velocity and not the acceleration). Sezawa et al did not provide any explanation just stated the claim. Clearly, as writing this paper, no one that this author seen has produced any, even remotely, reasonable model for this phenomenon if exist (coupling of transfer

properties of one DOF with non DOF).

Minorsky (1944) suggested that coupling occurs due to the effects of the propeller. While this conclusion is not explicitly stated but observed from equation (5), in his paper, and their subordinated equations (6-8). The combination of pitch and heave is too complicated for one article to critic and thus minimal discussion is offered. Jensen (2004) suggested the following equation for pitch–heave combination

$$2 \frac{kd}{\omega^2} \ddot{w} + \frac{a^2}{kb\alpha^3 \omega} \dot{w} + w = \alpha F \cos(\omega t) \quad (1)$$

And the equation for the angle (θ) in the pitch DOF is

$$2 \frac{kd}{\omega^2} \ddot{\theta} + \frac{a^2}{kb\alpha^3 \omega} \dot{\theta} + \theta = \alpha G \cos(\omega t) \quad (2)$$

where

Symbol	Definition
a	Amplitude
b	Width/breadth
d	Draught
F	External force
Fr	Froude number
G	External torque
s	Ship length
w	Undefined heave location

Greek Letters

α	$1 - Fr \sqrt{ks \cos \beta}$
β	Heading angle
ω	Angular velocity (undefined) \sqrt{kg}
θ	Pitch angle only in this equation

The eq. (1) and eq. (2) are similar but not really coupled the two DOFs. The only weak connection between the equations is the amplitudes, a . The logic of this connection is strange and several researchers, (Yamamoto, 1986 etc) suggest mathematical solutions. However, the problem is not mathematics, as hard as it get, but to find the actual physical mechanism that really controls the coupling which they totally failed to find. This case is another example where impressive mathematical skill cannot compensate for the lack of the physical rigorous and undersigning.

Additionally for the same reasons Riman (1946) attempts covered the same rational. Again papers such as by Ursell (1949) or (Korvin-Kroukovsky and Jacobs 1957) written by mathematicians who study the erroneous equations (math) to dictate the physics (physics was not considered as the leading role) thus, no real time should be award to these works. These works have

¹The horizontal movement for the specific cause of change of center of mass is neglected.

only value in the mathematical realm. There was an interest that only recently this author discovered that the von Karman's idea $d(mU)/dt$ was applied in one direction (DOF) while in other directions only the mdU/dt was applied, for example, Zarnick (Zarnick 1978). In Zarnick's paper, the schizophrenia is shown when in one hand the von Karman approach used while on the other hand the added mass matrix is used all the others DOFs (constant added mass).

There are many works like Haskin (1947) which are dealing pitch and heave. It is not clear why this combination of pitch heave seemed important. In fact, Hanaoka (1956) suggested that there is no connection but did not provided a real physics explanation or discussion. Even Newman (1957) in his thesis and several other papers discussed this connection clearly with the usual regular errors hence no point in analyzing his results. A summary of these works can be found in (Tasai 1960). As fashionable for that time, this interest faded within 4-6 years. Perhaps, it was due to the fact that nothing of significance was found or could be found while using the erroneous models.

The introduction of the added mass matrix was the most eventful which has presented and explained repeatedly in (Bar-Meir 2024c) and now it is urgent need to be uprooted. Landweber (1963) introduced the infamous erroneous of the added mass matrix which took over field. This error was augmented by Faltinsen and others in the early 197x to include rotational potential which meant that the added mass matrix grew in size from 3×3 to 6×6 matrix. It is fascinating that this information did propagate to Tasai (1971) as he ignored these accepted errors and built his model without this fundamentally fatal error. Additionally to minimize the jargon difficulty the following is repeated. The origin is at

FIGURE 1. A schematic of a ship to explain the ship motions names. Notice, that the origin is not clear (but should be for roll at the center of liquid level). The yaw rotation can be in different location other than the intersection of the roll and pitch (as the dotted line).

the point A (middle of liquid line at equilibrium and rsymmetrical bodies), the coordinate system pointing up (y direction), and does not rotate with the ship. Ship movements are called in the typical names; heave up and down and roll rotation around pivot

point have been adapted here. Note all the rotations might be not the origin.

3 Physics based Model

In this discussion, only physical argument are allowed and fairy tail realm reasoning is prohibited.

3.1 The Energies of Heave and Roll in Calm Liquid

A rsymmetrical large ship undergoes through a heave motion (up and down) in the same time undergoes rolling. Thus, the ship has several energies (why the word Th“large” was inserted? Think who is writing this paper.). It also assumed that there is no exterior horizontal force acting on the ship. Notice that the dimensional analysis is not offered here but will be provided with the almighty help in the stability book (Bar-Meir 2022b) some time in the future. The reader should be familiar with the standard Lagrangian mechanics. In this section the peculiarities of rolling and heave combination will be discussed.

In the derivation for a regular rsymmetrical body with a fix hinge has many terms that simply vanish. However, this scenario, when the hinge moves, has many more terms which affects the ship movement. Note that the negative sign was added to match the definition. To understand some of the issues consider a rod attached at the edge as shown in fig. 2 The rod is a

FIGURE 2. Rotating rod outside the mass centroid.

simplified version of the ship which (will be used as an example in the book) to the explain the physics rolling. The energy of a rod rotating around non centroid pivot point will be composed from the translational of the mass centroid and rotation energies. The purely translating energy without relative rotating velocity to mass centroid is $1/2mU_G^2$. The rotational energy is simply $1/2I_G\omega^2$ where subscript G mean mass centroid. An object spinning about non centroid point will have translational kinetic energy since it has momentum and the obvious rotational energy. At the rod centroid, the rod has a moment of inertia of $I_G = m\ell^2/12$ and $U_G = \omega\ell/2$. Where ℓ is the length of the rod and ω is the rotation speed at point A . At the hinge the energies

are

$$KE = \frac{1}{2}mU_G^2 + \frac{1}{2}I_G \omega = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}m \left(\frac{\ell \omega}{2}\right)^2}_{\text{translational}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \frac{m \ell^2}{12} \omega^2}_{\text{rotational}} = \underbrace{\frac{1}{6}m \ell^2 \omega^2}_{\text{total}} \quad (3)$$

In the same time, the kinetic energy at the pivot \mathcal{A} when noticing that the moment of inertia is $I_{\mathcal{A}} = m \ell^2/3$

$$KE = \frac{1}{2}mU_{\mathcal{A}}^2 + \frac{1}{2}I_{\mathcal{A}} \omega = 0 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{3}m \ell^2\right) \omega^2 = \frac{1}{6}m \ell^2 \omega^2 \quad (4)$$

The total kinetic energy is the same for both cases, but the proportion of translating and rotating depends on the relative point it is measured from. This example is trivial but the example provides a point. Additional point has to be noted in this rod example is that the hinge assumed to be fixed. For body with a moving hinge like the ship (body) total energy has to include the velocity (energy) of the moving hinge. Later, in this paper, this energy horizontal component will neglected for hand waving reasons under some situations/circumstances and simplifications. For clarification, the horizontal net force has to be zero per the assumption above. Thus, the hinge must move horizontally to satisfy this condition (which will ignored at this stage).

The definition of the “heave velocity” has to be clarified to remove ambiguity. While not explicitly defined in the establishment’s method (there are two), for the mass centroid the heave velocity seems to be defined as the velocity of the mass centroid in the heave direction (up and down). This author assumed that all the papers with the assumption of the rotation around the mass centroid are correct in this regards. For the papers that assumed that the pivot point to be at the metacenter, the calculations are wrong in addition to previously discussed points, the heave velocity is not properly defined. This definition is problematic (not wrong but the usage is wrong!) a frame of reference is fixed to the pivot point. In this article, the heave velocity is defined as the velocity of the pivot point \mathcal{A} as this point does not move in the sway (significantly) direction (x see fig. 1). A simple analysis suggests for a “free” hinge pendulum there is no horizontal velocity energy when there is no horizontal force. A survey of all found articles in this area shows that none of them consider this issue as many consider erroneously the pivot point to be around mass centroid (in some sense the mass centroid idea is wrong but consistent) or at metacenter. The sheer existence of the rolling forces the ship or the floating body also to sway as

the mass centroid moves in the sway direction x without external forces. In this series and other papers (Bar-Meir 2023g; Bar-Meir 2024b; Bar-Meir 2024c) this effect was not discussed (Why? To reduce the complications and increase acceptance to the already new material which “researchers” cannot challenge but insist on that their erroneous work was approved by “experts” reviewers.).

The rod can be replaced with a floating body which has a hinge/pivot point \mathcal{A} for rsymmetrical body. The rod mentioned in the above discussion can also represent a ship that rolled but without a fixed hinged point. In this case, the pivot point moves to keep the mass centroid in the same location because zero net force in the horizontal direction. While ultimately the poor man dimensional analysis suggests that this move is effectively and relatively small sometime but it does exist. For a thin body like the rod, this effect can be estimated as the moment acting at mass centroid is $m_r \omega \ell \cos \theta/2$ (m_r mass of the rod). The force can be estimated from Newton’s equation as

$$F = \frac{d(m_r U)}{dt} = m_r \frac{d \cos \theta \omega \ell/2}{dt} = \frac{m_r \ell \omega}{2} \left(\sin \theta \omega + \cos \theta \frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) \quad (5)$$

For small angles the force is

$$F \sim \frac{m_r \ell \omega}{2} \frac{d\theta}{dt} \quad (6)$$

This poor man dimensional analysis suggests, at some situations the force seems limited as ω and/or its derivatives are small. This idea is not precise and only shows the trend or even less and a proper dimensional analysis has to be done (but no time for that at this stage). Here there no discussion on the limitation of this analysis as not proper analysis which leads to questions about this point².

4 Physical Model

First recognizing the existence of the horizontal movement of the mass centroid due to rolling and second explaining that sometimes this movement can be neglected in the calculations. Notice that frame of reference is chosen so that the standard Lagrangian system and not additional terms have to added for accelerated system has to be used. Now the energies of the components of a ship can be expressed. As it was done in (Bar-Meir 2023g) the Lagrangian approach has to be employed under the same argu-

²It would be nice to get some help to carry this massive dimensional analysis on this point as almost all works that actually made progress in this area is done by this single individual.

ments. The general form of Lagrangian mechanics for two dimensional variables non-inertial system is

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{x}_i} = 0 \quad (7)$$

where x_i in this case are θ and y . Reusing the previously definition of Lagrangian, \mathcal{L} , which is

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U} \quad (8)$$

Where

Symbol	Definition
\mathcal{T}	the kinetic energy of the system
\mathcal{U}	the potential energy of the system.

This system did not analyzed extensively, thus every element is presented (to convince the agnostics as the main point in this paper to present the explicit meaning of the paper (Bar-Meir 2024c)).

4.1 Kinetic Energy

The kinetic energy, \mathcal{T} , is approximated around the hinge point as

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{(I_b + I_a) \dot{\theta}^2}{2} + \frac{(m_a + m_b) \dot{y}^2}{2} + \underbrace{(m_b + m_a) U_{\mathcal{A},x}(\theta)^2}_{\sim 0} + \dots \quad (9)$$

where

Symbol	Definition
I_a	Total added moment of inertia around point \mathcal{A}
I_b	Total body moment of inertia around point \mathcal{A}
m_a	Added mass
m_b	Body mass

Note that both moment of inertias are also a function of y but not \dot{y} or \ddot{y} which is the reason that y (not U) appears in eq. (9). Also note even though the velocity in the y direction is neglected, the added mass in x direction is different from the added mass in the y direction (actually the two velocities (accelerations) should be combined to find the actual added mass). The kinetic velocity is neglected in the y direction (it can be accounted but will make the calculations much more complicated), the \dots represents the linear kinetic energy due to change of orientation (see at (Bar-Meir 2023g) a close cousin of the added mass like the transport

properties. The change of the orientation causes ideal flow.). The vertical linear velocity \dot{y} is the velocity of point \mathcal{A} .

FIGURE 3. The change of buoyancy centroid, \mathcal{B} shown by large points and angles of the in angle θ and the out angle α for a body tilde counter clock wise for rectangular shape. The body is shown in two situations one at two situations (levels). Notice that while the input angles θ are the same, the output angles α are different different draught.

One of the mysterious and wonderful observation of thermodynamics is of water at -30°C or less at atmospheric pressure and yet the water is in the liquid phase. A small disturbance like a hit on the wall creates a freezing shock. The speed of the freezing speed is related to irreversible and unstable thermodynamics and similar situation exist in the heave movement. The stable situation is when the pivot point is at the liquid line. However, if for some reasons, the pivot point does not instantaneously move with the new liquid surface the situation is considered to be unstable. During the heave movement, the pivot point should change the pivot point location relative to the ship or the floating body. Thus, the distance \mathcal{AG} changes during heave process because the averaged liquid level changes or the body movement (point \mathcal{A}). For example, consider the cases shown in fig. 3 where the schematic on the left depicts the body at lower liquid level while the figure on the right exhibits body ship submersed deeper into the liquid because various reasons (wave, force, etc). While there is no evidence one way or another, it is assumed here that pivot point is always at the liquid surface level because it is the stable situation.

As in the strange situation like water in liquid phase well below the freezing point, the pivot point can be in an unstable situation (not in liquid line) but any disturbance triggers the system instantly to move to the stable point of the liquid surface (middle surface). And the system is highly dynamics and it is reasonable to consider the pivot point to be known at the said point.

4.2 Potential Energy

The potential energy due to the body mass centroid movement (or change), change of liquid level, and the potential energy due

to the transfer property are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U} &= \overbrace{w_{\mathbf{G}} (\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{G})|_y}^{\text{body}} - \overbrace{w_{\mathbf{B}} (\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}) \cos \alpha}^{\text{liquid}} \\ &= w_{\mathbf{G}} \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G} \cos \theta - w_{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} \cos \alpha \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

Where

Symbol	Definition
\mathbf{A}	Pivot point
\mathbf{B}	Submerged volume centroid
\mathbf{G}	Body mass centroid
w	Body/ship weight (also \mathbf{B} depends d)
Greek Letters	
α	in angle (see fig. 3)
θ	out angle (see fig. 3)

The weight w while pull out as the same, they are actually different (one is \mathbf{G} and the other \mathbf{B} which depends on d). Notice that in this case point \mathbf{A} is a function of time (the draught). Also notice that the body is assumed to be rsymmetrical. The distance \mathcal{K} (keel) to \mathbf{G} is constant (for a ship body). The draught distance, d , will be used later and can be written as

$$d = \mathbf{G}\mathcal{K} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G} \longrightarrow \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G} = d - \mathbf{G}\mathcal{K} \longrightarrow \dot{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{G} = \dot{d} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) means that the change of the draught, d , is identical to the change of $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{G}$. Notice that as opposed to the previous case (roll only) this value, here, d depends on time and its derivatives also. The output angle alpha, α , is the result for input angle θ as shown in fig. 3. This angle is defined precisely in (Bar-Meir 2022b). As a short statement, this angle is the angle between the line of the buoyancy centroid $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}_{new}$ and the ship center line for the change of the ship inclination by angle θ . The relation between α and θ depends on the geometry and the said change is given in reference (Bar-Meir 2022a) and (Bar-Meir 2022b) for several simple geometries. Since the geometry of the submerged part (due to the heave) modified (obviously, d changes) thus the output angle α changes. This relationship is a question determined by geometry and which can be supplied by the manufacture or can be calculated by the users. Thus, this relationship is treated as a given for any geometry.

There are two velocities in the y direction, the first is the point \mathbf{A} velocity in the frame of reference also denoted as U_y or \dot{y} and the second velocity is the liquid level velocity U_L . The relation between \dot{d} and heave velocity U_y and averaged liquid

level velocity, U_L can be written as

$$\dot{d} = U_y - U_L = \dot{y} - U_L \quad (12)$$

Where

Symbol	Definition
U_L	Liquid level velocity
U_y	Point \mathbf{A} velocity
\dot{y}	Point \mathbf{A} velocity

The vertical velocity of \mathbf{A} is denoted U_y and U_L both are positive in the up direction. The net change of the affecting parameter, d d/dt and/or d is due to the difference between these velocities. The frame of reference is attached to point \mathbf{A} at **equilibrium**. The velocity of the frame of reference is zero, 0. The derivation avoids using the plain U_y because it might necessitate integral type governing equations. The angles α and θ are actually not affected by the frame of reference. At equilibrium when $y = 0 \rightarrow d = d_0$ and when $y = \tilde{y} \rightarrow d = d_0 + \tilde{y}$ where \tilde{y} is the change in y and of course d_0 is the initial or equilibrium draught. The traditional approach is to conflate these two and here it will be done in the same way and \tilde{y} will be called simply y . Thus, the derivatives are the same $\dot{d} = \dot{y}$ (also see eq. (12)).

5 Governing Equations

The governing equations are obtained by applying the Laplacian equation eq. (7). There was no need to utilized the non-inertial and simple Laplacian equation was used.

5.1 The Derivation of Equation for y

Using the definition of eq. (7) carefully checking all terms. The process is divided into two parts as the first part contains the derivation with respect to y and the second part is derivations with respect to \dot{y} . This division in analysis is used to emphasis the physics. Notice as these derivations are carried, the mathematical interest is kept at minimum and a premium is payed for the physical understating.

5.1.1 The First Part For The y Equation

The first part for y reads

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial y} &= \left(\frac{\partial (I_b + I_a)}{\partial y} \right) \frac{(\dot{\theta})^2}{2} + \left(\frac{\partial (m_b + m_a)}{\partial y} \right) \frac{(\dot{y})^2}{2} \\ &\quad - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (w_{\mathbf{G}} \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G} \cos \theta - w_{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} \cos \alpha) \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

There are six terms (I_b , I_a , m_b , m_a , \mathbf{AG} , and \mathbf{AB}) that every one has to be analyzed. The first term using the parallel axis theorem for solid body reads

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial (I_b \dot{\theta}^2)}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(I_{bc} + m_b (\mathbf{AG})^2) \dot{\theta}^2 \right] = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}}_1 \underbrace{2 m_b \mathbf{AG}}_1 \frac{\partial (\mathbf{AG})}{\partial y} \dot{\theta}^2 = m_b \underbrace{(d - \mathbf{GK})}_{\mathbf{AG}} \dot{\theta}^2 \quad (14)$$

Where

Symbol	Definition
I_{bc}	Body moment of inertia at centroid point \mathbf{G}

The derivative of the moment of inertia of at mass centroid I_{bc} is zero because it is constant and not depend on y thus it is vanished. \mathbf{AG} is substituted in eq. (11) \dot{d} and $\partial U_L / \partial y = 0$ because U_L is not function of the y . It can be noticed that the body moment of inertia is independent of the angle or change of the angle or y . Notice, the establishment's scientists simply ignore this effect because their model is not physics based (a challenge to anyone in the establishment or else where to find a paper that consider this effect.). The second term is the derivative of added moment of inertia

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial (I_a \dot{\theta}^2)}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial ((I_{a0} + f(y)) \dot{\theta}^2)}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\theta}^2 \frac{\partial f(y)}{\partial y} \quad (15)$$

Where I_{a0} is moment of inertia relative to the center of liquid level at equilibrium and hence it is constant with respect to y . $f(y)$ is a function resulted from the geometry change of y . These values can be used or obtained from other tabulated added mass values for the geometry with a change of y . In the case of rectangular shape this value can be calculated from information given in (Bar-Meir 2022b). For example, in table 12.2 of the book provides a list of values for rectangular which can be used as approximation as a polynomial that yields the derivative values. The middle two terms become

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial ((m_a + m_b) (\dot{y})^2)}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{2} (\dot{y})^2 \frac{\partial m_a}{\partial y} \quad (16)$$

since the body mass, m_b , is constant. The next two terms are due to the potential energy as

$$-\frac{\partial \mathcal{U}}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial [(w_G \mathbf{AG} \cos \theta - w_B \mathbf{AB} \cos \alpha)]}{\partial y} = -w_G \cos \theta \frac{\partial \mathbf{AG}}{\partial y} + \mathbf{AB} \cos \alpha \frac{\partial w_B}{\partial y} + w_B \cos \alpha \frac{\partial \mathbf{AB}}{\partial y} + w_B \mathbf{AB} \frac{\partial \cos \alpha}{\partial y} \quad (17)$$

These two items (\mathbf{AG} and \mathbf{AB}) will be examined. These four terms suggest that each one contributes the governing equation as the first one as

$$\frac{\partial w_G \mathbf{AG} \cos \theta}{\partial y} = w_G \cos \theta \frac{\partial \mathbf{AG}}{\partial y} = w_G \cos \theta \quad (18)$$

The coefficient $\partial w_B / \partial y$ is unique as it represents the change of the buoyancy/"weight equivalent" of the ship at \mathbf{B} as the y change. Note that w_G is constant while w_B is variable. The simplest examination suggests that the force is at steady state immediately (like the frozen water story ignoring the acceleration, $\dot{d} < g$ supper poor analysis) beyond logic it is avoiding the complication even just for the simplicity sake. Thus, the buoyancy depends on the submerged volume while the actual weight of the ship is constant. While the derivative of weight is zero, the derivative of buoyancy can be written as

$$\frac{\partial w_B}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial (g \rho b d)}{\partial y} = g \rho b \quad (19)$$

Notice that the derivative with respect to w_B was taken. The value of \mathbf{AB} is a function of y , its derivatives, and the additional derivatives are also function of y . Also $\partial \alpha / \partial y$ is the function of the geometry which can be calculated or provided by the ship manufacture. As the derivative of d with respect to y is one.

The one before the last term in eq. (17) remains the same form as they provide the necessary information. The last term is

$$w_B \mathbf{AB} \frac{\partial \cos \alpha}{\partial \alpha} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y} = -w_B \mathbf{AB} \sin \alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y} \quad (20)$$

5.1.2 The second part for y Equation

The second part of the Laplacian for the y equation where the derivatives with respect to \dot{y} and the only terms left are evaluate

as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{y}} = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial}{\partial \dot{y}} \left((I_b + I_a) \frac{\dot{\theta}^2}{2} + (m_b + m_a) \frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} - (w_G \mathbf{A} \mathbf{G} \cos \theta - w_B \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \cos \alpha) \right) \quad (21)$$

The first terms (notice the formulation) are zero and thus only terms with the velocity properties are left as

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \left((m_a + m_b) \dot{y}^2 \right)}{\partial \dot{y}} = \frac{d}{dt} (m_a + m_b) \dot{y} = \frac{d m_a}{dt} \dot{y} + (m_a + m_b) \dot{y} \quad (22)$$

The angular energy does not contribute as well as the potential energy. Combining all the terms per eq. (7) yields The governing equation is

$$\left(m_b (d - \mathbf{G} \mathbf{K}) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial f(y)}{\partial y} \right) \dot{\theta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\dot{y})^2 \frac{\partial m_a}{\partial y} + \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \cos \alpha \rho b g - w_B \left(\cos \theta + \cos \alpha \frac{\partial \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}}{\partial y} + \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \sin \alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{d m_a}{dt} \dot{y} + (m_a + m_b) \dot{y} = 0 \quad (23)$$

This eq. (23) can be cleaned to read

$$(m_a + m_b) \dot{y} + \left(\frac{d m_a}{dt} + \frac{1}{2} \dot{y} \frac{\partial m_a}{\partial y} \right) \dot{y} + \left(m_b (d - \mathbf{G} \mathbf{K}) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial f(y)}{\partial y} \right) \dot{\theta}^2 + \rho b g \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \cos \alpha - w_B \left(\cos \theta + \cos \alpha \frac{\partial \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}}{\partial y} + \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \sin \alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y} \right) \quad (24)$$

Several observations can be made from eq. (24). The liquid level is affected by the \dot{y} and U_L as should be as opposed to the establishment's approach which does not account for these effects (at best it appears as a combined $\mathbf{G} \mathbf{M}$ or $\Delta \mathbf{G} \mathbf{M}$) formulae. The effect of point \mathbf{A} velocity is squared as oppose to establishment's that does not account this effect. The ship body counter appear (for example, $f(y)$) also in equation as the derive of α with respect to y appears in the equation. All the papers examined in this area, simply ignore these effects. All the derivatives with respect to y

are not independent of the solution of the equation as they are a function of the geometry only.

5.2 The Equation For θ

The derivative with respect to θ are carry similarity to eq. (13) but again the results are not symmetrical.

5.2.1 First part for θ

The mechanics of the derivations is the same for θ and the derivatives and six first terms are

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\frac{(I_b + I_a) \dot{\theta}^2}{2} + \frac{(m_b + m_a) \dot{y}^2}{2} - \frac{\partial (w_G \mathbf{A} \mathbf{G} \cos \theta - w_B \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \cos \alpha)}{\partial \theta} \right) \quad (25)$$

The mass and the moment of inertia of the body is not function of the θ hence vanish. Thus the derivative of first four terms yields

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial (I_a \dot{\theta}^2)}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial (m_a \dot{y}^2)}{\partial \theta} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial I_a}{\partial \theta} \dot{\theta}^2 + \frac{\partial m_a}{\partial \theta} \dot{y}^2 \right) \quad (26)$$

Terms that normally do not exist suddenly appear in the governing equations eq. (26). The establishment's approach neglects these elements of the physics of this problem. The derivatives with respect to θ of the last two terms reads

$$-\frac{\partial \mathcal{U}}{\partial \theta} = - \left(-w_G \mathbf{A} \mathbf{G} \sin \theta - w_B \frac{\partial \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}}{\partial \theta} \cos \theta + w_B \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \sin \alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \theta} \right) = + \left(w_G \mathbf{A} \mathbf{G} \sin \theta + w_B \frac{\partial \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}}{\partial \theta} \cos \theta - w_B \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \sin \alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \theta} \right) \quad (27)$$

Notice that $\mathbf{A} \mathbf{G}$ is not function of θ and hence the first term has only one derivative. The second term evolved into two parts. Normally, the kinetic energy does not add additional terms but the combination increases the number of terms. When there are more DOFs the equations get more complicated. The other two terms with the regular mass do not depend on y .

5.2.2 The Second Part of θ

For the second part of the Laplacian equation the results are

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\theta}} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial \left((I_b + I_a) \dot{\theta}^2 + (m_a + m_b) \dot{y}^2 \right)}{\partial \dot{\theta}} - \frac{\partial (w_G \mathbf{A} \mathbf{G} \cos \theta - w_B \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \cos \alpha)}{\partial \dot{\theta}} \right) \quad (28)$$

These six terms (I_b , I_a , m_b , m_a , $\mathbf{A} \mathbf{G}$, and $\mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}$) will be analyzed here. It can be noticed that the body mass or the body added moment of inertia are not affected by the angular velocity and thus they vanished. I_a , was discussed in (Bar-Meir 2023g, eq. 12) is vanished as it not depend only θ but not on $\dot{\theta}$. The first two terms read

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \left((I_a + I_b) \dot{\theta}^2 \right)}{\partial \dot{\theta}} = \frac{d \left((I_a + I_b) \dot{\theta} \right)}{dt} = \frac{d I_a}{dt} \dot{\theta} + (I_a + I_b) \frac{d^2 \theta}{dt^2} \quad (29)$$

The last two terms (the potential energy) vanish because they do not depend on the angular velocity.

The equation in θ direction is

$$(I_b + I_{add}) \frac{d^2 \theta}{dt^2} + \frac{d \theta}{dt} \frac{d I_{add}}{dt} - \left(w_G \mathbf{A} \mathbf{G} \sin \theta + w_B \frac{\partial \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B}}{\partial \theta} \cos \theta - w_B \mathbf{A} \mathbf{B} \sin \alpha \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \theta} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(\dot{y}^2 \frac{d m_a}{dt} + \dot{\theta}^2 \frac{d I_a}{dt} \right) = 0 \quad (30)$$

Equation (30) is the governing equation for the rolling plus the heave motion (minus the effects discussed earlier). Note the w_B is function of the time as oppose to w_G . The equations contains terms that previously were not known for the pure rolling motion situation. Further, these equation eqs. (24) and (30) are totally different from the equations that the establishment's "scientists" were solving for various boundary conditions. It is like losing a key in Chicago and looking for the key in Trondheim, Norway. Of course the solving the establishment's equations with the fantastic fairy added mass matrix which does not exist and missing the actual terms does not produce the real solution.

6 Comparison to Establishment

In this section a discussion on how the establishment's "scientists" using totally different equations that are not based on the physics and yet expect to get the same real physical results. The movement of the ship, according to the establishment, has to consider and take into account the added mass matrix elements. For example, Judge (2019) alleged that the linearised governing equations can be written as

$$\left(m + \overbrace{a_{33}}^{ud} \right) \overbrace{\ddot{x}_3}^{ud} + b_{33} \dot{x}_3 + c_{33} x_3 + \overbrace{a_{35}}^{ne} \ddot{x}_5 + \overbrace{b_{35}}{?} \dot{x}_5 + \overbrace{c_{35}}{?} x_5 = F(t) \quad (31)$$

In this section, the notations are 1 \rightarrow surge, 2 \rightarrow sway, 3 \rightarrow heave, 4 \rightarrow roll, 5 \rightarrow pitch, 6 \rightarrow yaw. The abbreviations are: *ud* means really undefined (pivot point possibly looks to be at the mass centroid according to the fairy realm), and, *ne* is not really existed, only in the fantasy realm like mixed added mass matrix coefficients. The question mark is to indicate that it is wrong but is not as the main concern for this stage and left as exercise for reader to demonstrate that these equations violate the second law of thermodynamics. Emphasizing the point of non existent: this term is resulted from the infamous error made by Landweber and extended by Faltinsen and associates and does not exist because the added mass matrix violates the second law of thermodynamics (Bar-Meir 2024c).

The second equation is for rolling (θ)

$$\overbrace{a_{42}}^{ne} \ddot{x}_2 + \overbrace{b_{42}}{?} \dot{x}_2 + \left(\overbrace{I_4}^{ud} + \overbrace{a_{44}}^{ud} \right) \overbrace{\ddot{x}_4}^{ud} + \overbrace{b_{44}}{?} \dot{x}_4 + \overbrace{c_{44}}{?} x_4 + \overbrace{a_{46}}^{ne} \ddot{x}_6 + \overbrace{b_{46}}{?} \dot{x}_6 + \overbrace{c_{46}}{?} x_6 = G(t) \quad (32)$$

where $G(t)$ is torque on ship (maybe?).

Now the examination of these linearised equations will be followed by simple questions which demonstrate that these equations do not make any physical sense. One must asks if one expect that these equations see only the mathematics or what the real physics predicts or participation. Beside extensive theoretical explanation provided in (Bar-Meir 2024c), here examination of the equations that control simple case of coupling heave-roll is presented. First the linearised equations is presented in this case by C. Judge (i.e. the original idea was not of Judge but by others so you cannot blame her for introducing this mistake as she just using it. Perhaps the main issue that she teaching these

and propagating these errors.).

Equation (31) claims that the added mass is constant, and only that the pitch affects the movement of the heave. The roll DOF does not have any effect on heave which make no physical sense. In fact a poor man dimensional analysis suggests the opposite i.e. the roll has a strong effect as compared to the pitch. Thus, according to C. Judge and others, the rolling does not affect the heave and heave does not affect the rolling. Basically, this claim deny the existence parametric rolling. This conclusion is in a directly contradiction all works in the field, logic, and observational evidence that anyone can be done by anyone. Indirectly Judge's equations suggest that the shape of the ship does not effect the added mass (how this claim even possible, well in the place where fairies work it might.).

Techet (Techet 2005) followed others in her class notes (that again she is not the creator of the error but followed others). Basically the formation for heave (DOF number 3) and roll (DOF number 4) should appear as

$$-F_3 = m_{33} \frac{dU_3}{dt} + m_{34} \frac{dU_4}{dt} \quad (33)$$

and

$$-F_4 = m_{43} \frac{dU_3}{dt} + m_{44} \frac{dU_4}{dt} \quad (34)$$

Note in the establishment's attempt to force uniformity has certain consequence, F_4 is a torque and m_{44} is moment of inertia etc. Note that m_{34} is the half horse and half fairy living on dreadful lane. The dimensional analysis suggests that this mixing (force and torque and etc) simply creates twilight light physics (again equivalent of half man and half horse). Let the mixed units mess lay a side, the main point is that the physics, in this presentation, is detached from reality. Furthermore, this claim is so wonderful that a single force creates a torque. This presentation dictates that the real extra force due to the change of d does not have any effect on the situation. Clearly, this omission is wrong as that is the main mechanism that controls the coupling. The establishment's model (assuming that it can be called this way) suggests that the coupling is constant regardless to physics as the added mass matrix coefficients are constant.

The eq. (31) basically states that the added mass does not change even though von Karman (1929) and others like Lu et al (2024) and their previous almost duplicates claims that is not possible. In fact, this schizophrenic approach that C. Judge used in other papers and others discussed in this paper cannot coexist (maybe in a fantasy realm where fairy and supper magical creatures do thrive.).

6.1 Remarks on the ΔGM

The reality dictates that the change in heave manifest in a change of draught and consequences. As the establishment's "science" constrains, the situation is basically irrelevant and as the effects should be covered by the added mass matrix (see for example Judge's or Techet's classes notes). Some realized how ridicules the establishment's approach, hence some come out with innovative ideas while not realizing that they are suggesting is wrong as relying on broken foundations is never a good thing. Yet, it is much better than the establishment idea that the heave has fixed effects based the added mass matrix.

The characterized by a change in the force upward in the heave movements, some assume that the changed of the forced during the heave movement is at of gravity (mass centroid), G , and of G value. However, this force, G , is fixed as magnitude and origin regardless to the wave or change of the draught. Ghadimi (2013) suggested to "absorbed" the force by the wave forces as the gravity gained or lost via this mechanism (read the sarcastic tone of the author). This idea as opposed to (2024) in equation (11) of that paper claiming that $x_G m r^2$ in the x direction while in the y direction the force is $x_G m dtr$. The dimensional analysis suggests that something fundamentally wrong with terms in this equations set. This kind nonsense is typical of people how did not have studied proper dimensional analysis, yet it is ignored here as the main inquiry is to understand whether their fundamentals errors did prevent the understand the draught effect. Well, they have no clue what was going in the area. In fact, many of the authors of these papers observed reading Potto Project various publications, and yet they pretend these publications were never published. This belief is worst of anyone that would like to be considered as as a scientist (on this list is plagiarism, ignorance, super stupidity, just waste of resources etc.).

The idea that von Karman (1929) transfer of energy is based on the change momentum in reality the added mass mass (even though it might be under circumstance the same or just look the same). For example, Lu et al (2023), suggested the entire (2D) layer is absorbing momentum/energy. The added mass concept is based on the idea that the body push some liquid in order to allow the proportion of itself and the pushed mass moves as the body moves. This material is the added mass and that is the only material that should participated in the equations or the calculations. Thus, this over excessive material should be controlled (or limited) more with this idea in mind.

Hirris (not sure about the author(s) name or the version) (2022) suggested a nice analysis to consider the effect the buoyancy change (around eq. 6-15). Yet, he failed to consider the added mass change (of the floating body). As clearly understood, the change of the floating body even the change of the submerged volume must change the added mass of the body. Additional point, while recognizing the change of B is commendable, fact remains that for other DOFs the change occurs at B which is not fixed and not at G . For example, this error appears in eq. (6-28) G

is fixed and \mathbf{B} is the variable beside several other errors. The last point is the issue of stability which did get the attention because the author(s) are clueless about this point.

7 Body Initial and Boundary Conditions and Conditions

While eqs. (24) and (30) provides the frame on which solutions should be built, boundary conditions and/or the initial conditions are needed. While the situation can be elliptic (depends on only boundary condition), in some situations, the prevailing characteristics is parabolic (that is the combination of the boundary and initial conditions is required). There are very little hyperbolic situations in marine engineering that this author is ware of (for example, movement of the pivot point). After this physical jargon (using mathematical terms) introduction (sorry have hard time to simplify this topic) a discussion on what type of problems commonly encountered. The extreme cases are the slamming which the body moves from the gas phase to liquid phase and the opposite from the liquid phase to the gas phase (marine creatures leaping out the liquid). Between these two extreme cases, many complicate situations can occur.

7.1 Parametric Rolling

In this section review of important papers or recently symbolic papers is presented. One of the way the establishment presented or pretends that there is value to an erroneous work by ignoring and pretending conflicting works do not exist, so that they do not have to justify their erroneous work. There are several explanations to why and where there parametric rolling. Indication that no one understand the situation is when proponent of the model do not “argue” between the groups as in this case.

The following quote is a recent example how the claims of the mysterious box work against the logic.

Quotations

Parametric instability is the gradual build-up of excessively large rolling created by a mechanism of internal forcing, the result of a fluctuating restoring that depends on where the ship lies in relation to the wave (ABS, 2019). This phenomenon is related to the periodic change of stability as the ship moves in longitudinal waves at a speed when the ship’s wave encounter frequency is approximately twice the rolling natural frequency and the damping of the ship to dissipate the parametric roll energy is insufficient to avoid the onset of a resonant condition.

Reference: Spyros Hirdaris

The parametric rolling usually refers to the conditions where the ship undergoes a heave (DOF) and a rolling motion ap-

pears without any application of torque or external source. Hirdaris’s claims that this description hold true for other motions as well. Without going through one cannot wonder where the buildup that Hirdaris suggesting occur, how and in what mechanism? Is there a buildup absorbing property in the liquid or solid or the combination of the sold body and liquid maybe invisible springs? Maybe instability occurs at the double the unknown ship frequency which no one know?

The review shows that there are several reasons why people believe the parametric rolling occurs. One of the most common explanation (no, it is not these invisible springs/capacitors) is the non-linearity causes introduce this extra movement of rolling. The literature review shows that the non-linearity by itself does not cause instability in many other situations. This author disputes the notion that the nature hates non-linear mathematics and hence changes conditions/situations to unstable just due to complexity. There is no reason to believe that the nature “hates” complex or non linear equations. The notion that Hirdaris’ idea that it is build up promote make no sense if one expect that this “build-up” has to accumulate somewhere (maybe in the æther). The physics itself forces instability when it deserved to be unstable (see several example in (Bar-Meir 2022a). Here is a short list of the instability in fluid mechanics and has fundamental physical explanation: turbulence, Rayleigh–Taylor instability, Dean instability etc.

Another common explanation is to blame the creation of parametric rolling on the waves or the wind. This explanation is more common and has some logic but it does not answer why sometime it occurs while in other times or other ship it does not appear. The explanation is double down on the special waves or winds. Yet, the parametric roll does not occur to all ship and floating bodies. Thus, beside the wave(s) or wind there must be another factor or factors that was ignore until now. Thus, the search for the reason(s) must be on the physics realm. Once the physical reason is found or analyzed, next question is at what rate, and under what conditions this instability occurs? If the rate is a kind of instantaneous change, then the above equations regulate/control the situation like the transition from laminar to turbulent flow. While in the extreme case like filling process in die casting (Bar-Meir 2021; Bar-Meir 2023e), this case the steady state is more important. This statement is made without a proper dimensional analysis as it just simply based on the logical arguments (not experimental proof).

The fundamental question of ship stability is when a ship stays in the preferred position and not “flips” to other undesirable positions. For example, a wooden rectangle (in this case the square) floats on water when the density ratio $\bar{\rho} \sim 0.5$ is inherently unstable (the body preferred situation should be faced up in the chosen direction which up see the fig. 4 but reality is at angle.). This question was solved in (Bar-Meir 2022b) which shows the typical stability dome shown fig. 4. The area under the dome line is unstable marked with the pink color while the

FIGURE 4. Stability diagram for rectangular prisms. The dark magenta line show the change of the draught (density).

area about the dome line is stable (white color). When value of d changes, for what ever reason, effectively it is for the stability analysis akin to change of the density. For instance, when the body is about ($d = 0.5D$) the density is $\rho_s/\rho_l \sim 0.5$. However, when ($d = 0.75D$) the density ratio changes to $\rho_s/\rho_l \sim 0.75$. Examining the diagram for the case where b/D is constant a change on the density from one value to another can be translated the ship into the unstable dome. This mechanism is the only one that is physics based proposed in the literature as writing this words.

7.2 Ship Slamming

Ship slamming refers to either to a body moves into the liquid (water) from the gas (air phase). This situation is basically an initial conditions problem with the boundary conditions which acting as absorbing the energy. The phase change of the surrounding liquid involve change of the added mass as the main mechanism which slow or even stop the body (ship). This situation is example of initial condition (ship velocity) and the added mass increases which slow down the body. In this situation the ship or the floating body is rapidly displaces the liquid (rapid heave) and by doing so increase the added mass. While the slamming can be three dimensional, in this section is limited to two dimensional situations. The three dimensional also might involve rapid pitch even a simple list (changing the equilibrium) which change the characteristics of the situations.

The regular harmonic is different from periodic situation where the reducing in the size of the righting force is the only mechanism that claimed by the establishment’s scientists. The main mechanism that controls the slowing down is the increase of the term dm_a/dt or dm_a/dy . This change in the connection of a coupling of two degree of freedom might cause a possible instability in heave which creates rolling. The analysis of this effect shows conflicting trends and so far no conclusive words can be said on this point.

7.3 Out of the Liquid

The opposite to the action of the slamming is getting/jumping out the liquid. The reverse direction, the issue is a body is moving up (heave) like dolphins or other creates has somewhat opposite reaction. Such case can be of a marine creature jumping out of water or sea water. All the analysis and experimental observation show that in this case, parametric is almost eliminated. This observation of logic as the apparent density is approaching to zero and hence the body because more stable (see fig. 4). In that case, the added mass decreases and the question of stability is moot. That is, in the case negative added mass coefficient stabilize the situation while positive added mass make it, in some situations, unstable. This physical observation is not conclusive but seem reasonable. In that cases, the creature moves with an angle of attack and which the gravity affecting the movement might leap out the liquid without any instability issue. Additionally, when the added mass is decreasing due to the (momentum conservation) increasing the velocity (see the octopus story Triantafyllou and colleagues). Notice the process is not exactly linear or reversible. That is the body that slams into the liquid (water) will not have the same energy when it moves up (or in angle). That is, the second law makes our life more difficult.

8 Summary

This paper that started due to the cursing letters received from several minions/“independent researchers” who strongly felt the need to insult this author so that they feel good about their erroneous work. Since they admit that this author did produce new material but if there is new material it must be erroneous (see for example, Mathias Marley some of his explanations). One assumes that these letters comes with territory and that is okay. In the explanation of these concepts (in this paper) it becomes clear that they should be present to the general public. The same can be said to the transfer properties papers it looks clear to this author but some do see as clearly wrong.

The establishment’s scientists governing equations contain the mass matrix as the main part. This paper change and fix the governing equations (actuality it was done in (Bar-Meir 2024c)). In doing so, this paper will change the course of the research in navigation from nonsense to science. Now, it is clear that there is no added mass matrix and the mixed coefficients don’t exist even in heave–roll combination. For example, check the contrast between the establishment’s scientists idea and this author’s work added mass matrix. A imperfect cylinder with mixed added mass coefficients according to establishment’s “scientists” during the heave affects to sway sway motion while this author claim none of it. Clearly the establishment’s idea is a pure garbage. So, the establishment’s theory is wrong and violates the Newton’s second law and opposite reactions to the what really happening.

Now, why this error occurred and who are responsible for these worthless, useless, and fallacies research works have not

been reported. According google scholar some these individuals have over 50k citations most if not all erroneous works with position of editors of journals. Clearly citing a garbage is pure gold and your paper will accepted does not make your work worth something but make it suspicious of trash quality. It shames that these errors went so far to this point. This paper is a specific coupling example between the heave and roll heavy discussed. In a way, the real relations are shown for specific case of heave and roll which contradict the establishment's idea.

Prediction

It is not very common to write an article that basically revolutionized the whole field by changing the governing equations. This revolution was done in the previous article in this series. This author has already done one revolution in die casting where he changed the whole field upside down. The question that raise how long it will take to change the majority to field to used the correct technology. In die casting it took about 35 years where the establishment basically had major controlled over the publishing avenues. Initially in the process and as results of conflict, this author faced many obstacles. Later the main location (Ohio State University) seems to be melting away because the shame of the trashy research work that done by the main faculty of that time because all was exposed.

The question how long it will take to adapt the correct governing equations (new technology). There are those who publicly put their head in the sand such as Faltinsen, Fossen, and Carlos Guedes Soares, and Skjetne and several Korean and Japanese researchers. For example consider Petacco (2024) as writing this paper, arm with the knowledge that at least their ideas are "challenged" or better description is claimed to be completely trash and yet they cannot defined the pivot point, ignore the added mass change, etc. See for example equation (5) in the paper. It hard to believe that they themselves do believe that they are writing. While in die casting, this stage disappeared very fast, here in a large field like marine engineering this pretend ignorance will take longer. For one, the research grants in die casting are only less on 1% as compared to marine engineering which is about 5–20 billions dollars. They, in marine engineering, will be able to produce erroneous research for much longer. See for example, the assistant editor Chris Kent's "suggestion" to let his colleagues (with lack of knowledge) to judge this author's work. With the forgoing it seems even with how fast information pass today the process seem to take about 10 years. It will be interesting to see if this prediction will turn out to be reasonably correct.

Disputation

After the minion Mathias Mathias from Norwegian University of Science and Technology and probably his masters (it hard to believe graduate student done it by himself) claiming that either

all was known or if it was not known it must be wrong, here is a challenge for this minion and his masters and the other minions. Additionally there are those quietly belief in these claims without advertise their belief. Furthermore, there are those who put the horse blindfold to minimize their exposure the new technology like Carolyn Q. Judge so they will not realize their work was useless/wrong. With about five billion (at least) dollars a year in research grants and producing research papers that violate the second law of thermodynamics it is time to examine these claims. This author is calling for disputation since the subject is science and true matter, hopefully. If you believe in one or more of the topics below you have an invitation for disputation.

These topics are

1. The pivot point of the rolling or pitching is either in the metacenter or mass centroid or "rolling center" or "somewhere between the metacenter and gravity centroid" or in the "aether". The rolling center mentioned in this series.
2. If you believe that there are really added mass matrix. In other words, if you believe that there are m_{ji} and (a_{ij}) terms.
3. The moment of inertia is independent of the pivot point.
4. Added mass or the added moment of inertia is constant. As the governing equations as defined in Fossen or MIT or Caroline Judge's classes.
5. The pivot point is fixed in the ship navigation equations.
6. If you believe that MMG equations are correct or logical or sensible.
7. If you believe the strip theory as is described or is correct as in MIT's classes .
8. If you believe that added mass is not actually a single added mass (a core belief in the common establishment's doctrine). In other words, if you believe that the added mass matrix is correct.
9. If you believe that more 20% of the world research in the ship stability/navigation does not violate the second law of thermodynamics or Newton's second law.
10. GM is the correct righting arm of the ship.

Acknowledgment

This paper describe a progress in this kind of magnitude has some willing and unwilling partners. First, thank you for Naomi Marshak who corrected the English of early draught of the first 3 pages which her questions added more material. No one can clean all the English errors that this authors capable to produce, Second, the unwilling participants such as Carolyn Q. Judge from USNA that set to "protect" her students from the truth. Mathias Marley his lack of understating and willingness to curse this author brought this paper. At least as opposed to the other minions who demand to remain anonymous, he was willing to show his name. The treasure trove that Larrie Ferreiro gave is so large that at one point this author was contemplating making him

as co-author. Discovery of the added mass effects, 1) Fitzgerald, 2) Lautrup, 3) von Karman, 4) Weymouth and Triantafyllou (others), and 5) This author. Notice while all independent elements the other authors discovered are different.

As example of fad's believer Dr. Song provided inspiration on how one can double down on stupidity is so amusing. Some discussion elements on parallel theorem remained and persist in this paper please ignore those. There are those to contribute via discussions but asked to remain anonymous, thank you! Also thank you to Kostas Spyrou by his plagiarizing demonstrated how the establishment deals with the "rogue agent" by netscaping his/their material.

About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made and on how many people plagiarized his work. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing these discoveries. The irony is that these author's models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, this servant solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation).

Bar-Meir was instrumental in developments of the added mass (properties) concepts. He has differentiated between the added properties and the transfer properties. He discovered the change of the added mass and its effects on the governing equations. He invented the stability dome for floating bodies and in the process developed the equation for centroid of circle segment.

Kostas J. Spyrou, when he gave his keynote lecture, basically copied many concepts that were developed by Bar-Meir (such as the stability dome) and presented them as his ideas. These concepts had never appeared in the literature before. It is interesting to point out that Dr. Spyrou has been observed downloading Bar-Meir's book. Dr. Spyrou's behavior is not unique to him only. Dr. Kenneth Brezinsky went out of his way to declare that Bar-Meir's calculations of compressible gas potential were useless and baseless. However, Brian J. Cantwell from Stanford

University recently decided to copy Bar-Meir's idea and to dedicate a whole section (2.9) to it in his book (and probably also in his classes) to this idea. Except that Dr. Cantwell oversimplified the idea (he removed the dimensionless presentation), maybe because he did not fully understand it. The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to discoveries of this author.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar-Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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